

The Use Of Digital Tools In The English Classroom In Spain

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APA Citation:

Rubio, A.D.J., Conesa, I.M.G., (2022). The Use Of Digital Tools In The English Classroom In Spain , *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 18(3),214-236; 2022.

Submission Date: 09/05/2022

Acceptance Date: 15/08/2022

Abstract

In recent years, the rapid growth of information and communication technologies and social networks has radically changed our lives. The digital revolution has had a positive impact on all areas of society, especially in education, allowing students to improve their communication and language skills. Today, knowledge is on the web and teachers are the ones in charge of guiding the students in their learning process. For this reason, the teachers' work is more important than ever; their role needs to be reconsidered and they must be ready for the challenges of a digital education. This study aims to be a tool to guide their steps towards a teaching prepared for society challenges, in which, as we have seen in recent years, at any time face-to-face teaching can falter. Teachers must make an effort and prepare themselves for the teaching of the future. Methodology, resources, tools and even evaluation must be adapted to the new era. This paper focuses on the integration of digital tools in English as a foreign language classroom. Its main objective is to design a program based on the development of digital competences of English language teachers. To this end, the evolution of the use of digital tools in the educational field and more specifically in the teaching of foreign languages will be scrutinized, analyzing the main advantages and disadvantages of their integration in the classroom. As for the program, the starting point will be an initial assessment based on the collection of information through a questionnaire to assess the digital competence of teachers. Moreover, activities aimed at teachers of our school English department are developed in order to put into practice the tools that will be analyzed throughout the program.

Keywords: digital tools; digital competence; FL teaching guide; teaching technology.

1. Introduction

Since the end of the 20th century and especially in the 21st century, the use of technology has increased exponentially, expanding globally and drastically changing our lives. This profound change has also extended to the field of education with the aim of approaching the learning process in a totally different way and ensuring that students achieve knowledge that lasts over time. In today's world, young people

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are considered digital natives, since they were born and raised surrounded by technology. (Godwin-Jones, 2005). In addition, in the last two years the importance of digital tools in teaching has experienced a great rebound due to the appearance of COVID-19. Therefore, globalization and the situation experienced since March 2020 in Spain have helped to find and use new approaches for teaching in general, but also for teaching English as a foreign language. Most of these approaches make use of new technologies, which are increasingly being used in the English classroom.

When it comes to teaching and especially the acquisition of a foreign language, new technologies can be of great help to foreign language learners. As Murray (2005) states, the use of technology makes students more autonomous and more motivated, as well as helping to build a solid base of collaboration and interaction between teachers and students. It is undeniable that the use of digital tools such as the Internet, applications, blogs, chats, computers, mobile phones and tablets has become a fundamental part of students' daily lives. Taking into account all of the above, it is important to take advantage of technological resources to achieve the objectives that arise in the teaching of English. Students of English as a foreign language need extra linguistic help, they need to practice listening and speaking, reading and writing to improve their language skills (Ybarra and Green, 2003). To achieve these goals, they need to use many tools that help them learn the English language effectively and with as little effort as possible. Among the wide variety of tools available to students today, we can identify the tools of Web 2.0, the social networking platforms that have changed our lives in the last decades. In general, social networks have become tremendously effective means of communication thanks to their ease of use and their great accessibility, being within the reach of anyone with a mobile phone. The use of social networks such as Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, to name just a few, has become an everyday thing for users belonging to any age, social or professional group in order to maintain contact with friends and acquaintances or to be informed of any event that occurs worldwide. However, not only can these media be useful in our daily lives, but they can also be used for pedagogical purposes such as facilitating the teaching and learning of the English language (Liu et al., 2015).

Therefore, the main objective of this research paper is to design a teaching program based on the needs detected in terms of teaching the digital competence. From this primary objective, we can also pose some other secondary objectives such as to develop activities in accordance with the program designed, to plan different sessions, and to conduct the evaluation of the program.

1.1. Literature review

This chapter briefly summarizes the theoretical framework that has led to the creation of this work, exploring the history of technology and how it began to be used in the teaching-learning of English as a foreign language. Likewise, it provides a review of the scientific literature, delving into relevant studies regarding the attitude and motivation of students with respect to the topic that concerns us.

In recent decades, pedagogy has undergone a profound paradigm shift, moving from passive learning to active learning (Shenninger, 2018). Along the same lines, socio-constructivist theory states that learners build their learning of a foreign language through social interaction and self-reflection on their own experiences (Simina & Hamel, 2005). Specifically, this theory is based on the theories of Piaget and Vygotsky, suggesting that the teaching process is based on prior knowledge and experience (Kaufman, 2004). Therefore, learning becomes a productive-active process in which newly acquired knowledge is combined with previous mental schemes (Kaufman, 2004; Simina & Hamel, 2005). For this reason, learning must be oriented towards the student and not towards the teacher. Additionally, socio-constructivism emphasizes collaboration and negotiation of thinking and learning. According to Piaget et al. (1984), individual knowledge depends on its social construction.

Related to the social aspect of constructivism, there is another socio-educational theory, the sociocultural theory. The main defender of this theory is Lev Vygotsky for whom the influence of the society and culture in which the language learner lives during the language acquisition process is essential: social interaction and the environment are the most important factors in the process of learning and acquiring a language. The most outstanding features of the sociocultural theory are the concepts of mediation, "scaffolding", the zone of proximal development (ZPD) and collaborative interaction.

According to Lantolf (2000), mediation describes the relationship between the human being and the world. People use physical and psychological tools to build this relationship, so language learning becomes a social process, based on the person's mediating cognitive tools. In an educational context, during social and collaborative interaction, both the teacher and the students provide a "scaffolding", a support that allows the student to access the zone of proximal development. According to Vygotsky, the zone of proximal development is the difference between the level of actual development of the student and his potential development. Most importantly, the linguistic process involves social interaction and collaboration between learners and the social environment: peers, teacher, and parents (collaborative interaction), while the sociocultural approaches of mediation and the zone of proximal development facilitate the whole process (Tanaka, 2005).

Behaviorism has its roots in the works of Edward Thorndike (1913) and Pavlov (1927), which were later developed by Skinner (1938). The main assumption of the theory of behaviorism is that each organism depends on the influence that the environment exerts on it and, as a result, its behavior is shaped by external factors. Behaviorists take only external factors into account and ignore any interpretation based on the internal mental processes of individuals. Furthermore, in the context of language acquisition, learning is defined as the process of changing the student's behavior through exercises set by the teacher. Effective learning, which is the goal of teaching, is achieved through positive reinforcement (reward) or negative reinforcement (punishment).

Behaviorism has been a hugely influential paradigm during the 20th century in many educational systems. It has influenced the teaching process by formulating principles to define and develop pedagogical and didactic objectives that must be very specific and clear. It has also had a great influence on the design and use of information and communication technologies (ICT), since this theory was based on computer teaching. Although in recent years behaviorist approaches to knowledge and learning are no longer at the forefront of educational software design, as they have given way to a more constructive and sociocultural type of teaching, their overall contribution to this area of research should be recognized, mainly in the light of a didactic design.

Since technology is constantly being implemented in the educational system, more and more educators need to be informed and trained on how to use technological tools in the teaching process. In this sense, Mishra and Koehler (2006), researchers at Michigan State University, established the model of Technical Pedagogical Content Knowledge or TPACK (Technology, Pedagogy and Content Knowledge), in the absence of another theory capable of explaining or guiding the effective integration of educational technology. The TPACK model is based on Schulman's notion of Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK, 1986). Schulman suggested that knowledge should go beyond the content of each subject by introducing the dimension of teaching. Therefore, both the contents and the way of presenting these contents would be included to facilitate their understanding, that is, the most common way of teaching them, through figures or conceptual maps, analogies, common errors, etc.

Specifically, the TPACK model, which focuses on technological knowledge (TK), pedagogical knowledge (PK) and content knowledge (CK), presents a creative approach to many of the issues teachers face when implementing educational technology in their classrooms. By differentiating between these three types of knowledge, the TPACK model describes how content (what is taught) and pedagogy (how the teacher conveys that content) should form the basis of any efficient integration of

educational technology. This order is quite significant, since the technology that is implemented must be able to transmit the content while supporting the pedagogy, in order to improve the learning experience of the students.

According to the TPACK model, specific technological tools (hardware, software, applications, etc.) are of great help in instructing and guiding students towards a better and more solid understanding of the subject. The three types of knowledge, technological, pedagogical and content, are combined and recombined in different ways within the TPACK model. Technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK) describes the relationships and interactions between technological tools and specific pedagogical practices, while pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) describes the relationship between pedagogical practices and specific learning objectives. Furthermore, technology content knowledge (TCK) describes the relationships and intersections between technologies and learning objectives. These three areas constitute the TPACK, which must interact in a meaningful way to facilitate the process of teaching and learning languages.

Figure 1: Representation of the TPACK model

Source: Own elaboration

Since its inception in 2006, the TPACK model has become one of the leading theories of educational technology integration, on which much research and professional development is based. Finally, one of the main advantages of the TPACK model is that it leaves room for researchers and practitioners to adapt their theoretical framework to different circumstances.

Computer-assisted language learning (CALL) is an academic field that explores the role of information and communication technologies in language learning and teaching. This term came into use in the 1960s in the United States (Thomas, Reinders & Warschauer, 2012). According to Levy (1997, p. 1), computer-assisted language learning is “an approach to language teaching and learning in which computer technology is used to aid in the presentation, reinforcement, and assessment of material to be learned, which often includes a substantial interactive element”. Due to the incorporation of portable digital devices into our lives, the term “CALL” has become an essential component of teaching and research in the field of languages.

The history of computer-assisted language learning unfolds in 3 stages (Stevie, 2011). The first appeared in the 1950s and continued throughout the 1970s and was called “structural/behavioral CALL” (Warschauer, 1996), based on the repetitive visualization of similar materials. In particular, Warschauer (1996, pp. 3-4) points out: “The main feature of this approach is that the computer is perfect for practicing repetitive exercises. The computer acts as an instructor, showing the material and evaluating the activities individually, in this way, the students move at their own pace”.

In the 80s and 90s the “communicative/cognitive CALL” appeared. At this stage, computers were used to encourage conversation or writing (Warschauer, 1996). Students focused on producing authentic expressions rather than handling set phrases. The programs did not offer feedback to the students on their mistakes and accepted a different set of answers than those offered by the computer (Warschauer, 1996).

The last stage is the “Integrative/Sociocognitive/Socioconstructive CALL”, which was adopted in the 2000s and continues to exist today. It is in this period where it has acquired its full potential. The development of the Internet and hypermedia that combine video and audio transmission, interactive graphic content and virtual worlds have reconfigured the way of learning. This type of computer-assisted language teaching creates realistic learning conditions by taking advantage of various tools, in which language skills are combined and authentic, synchronous and asynchronous means of communication are facilitated. Students can communicate directly, cheaply and easily with other foreign students or native speakers anytime, anywhere (Warschauer, 2004).

Studies on the process of teaching a foreign language with the help of the computer have shown that it is an instrument that improves teaching and learning. This method increases input and facilitates language practice, acting as a platform for intercommunication, improving interaction between students. Along the same lines, Kelm (1998) argues that computer teaching helps students to practice foreign languages in authentic situations, while promoting socialization and communication between them.

After computer-assisted language teaching, Network Based Language Teaching (NBLT) made its appearance, in which students could practice the language, individually or collectively, connected to a local network or global. Online language teaching emerged with the arrival of technological and educational advances. In the 1980s and 1990s, network technology and infrastructure developed rapidly in many industrialized countries, making low-cost connections possible. At the same time, educational theory and practice were further affected by social constructivism, which emphasized the social and cultural construction of knowledge, the importance of cooperation between individuals and groups, and an approach to education based on the interests of the students.

Over the last few years, the Internet itself has changed dramatically thanks to the rapid advancement of collaborative tools and sites that promote social networking, interactive gaming, collaborative writing and editing, and multimodal production. These tools offer students the possibility to read, write, communicate and build knowledge in a second or foreign language in a new and unexplored way.

Technology and the teaching of English are related to each other (Singhal, 1997). In the 1960s and 1970s, various educational institutions used English learning labs made up of small cabinets, equipped with a cassette deck, microphone, and earphone for each student. The teachers used a central control panel to observe the interaction between the students. One of the advantages of this type of technology was that the oral production of the students allowed them to learn English quickly. Although the concept of language laboratories was a positive way of linking technology with the teaching and learning of the English language, students found the audio-linguistic method monotonous and boring (Singhal, 1997). Another problem that contributed to the failure of this technique was that the interaction between the teacher and the students was minimal.

In recent years, with the spread and development of English, being the most widely spoken language in the world, the number of English learners has increased considerably. Due to the continuous advancement of technology, the teaching and learning of English has changed completely. Gradoll (1997, p. 79) highlights the importance of technology in the spread of the English language: “Technology is at the center of the globalization process; affects education and culture. The use of the English language increased exponentially after 1960”. Currently, English is the language of the social, political, sociocultural context, the language of business, education, industry and the media, having become the language most studied as a foreign language.

Today, technology offers many options, as it makes the process of teaching and learning the English language more interesting and productive. It is one of the most important engines of social and linguistic change. In other words, it offers many opportunities for learners of English to develop their communicative competence.

2. Method

The center selected for piloting this project is a public center, located in the fishing village of San Pedro del Pinatar, in the south of the Region of Murcia. It is a municipality that has a population of 26,320 inhabitants (according to the municipal census of 2021), which bases its economic activity on the service sector and small businesses, despite its fishing and agricultural tradition. Our center is located in the neighborhood of "Los Antolinos".

The history of the institute is closely linked to that of the town. At the end of the 19th century, the town began to be one of the favorite places for the Spanish upper bourgeoisie to build their summer residences. It was one of these families who years later ceded some land for the construction in 1978 of the "*Escuela de Mastería Industrial*", the seed of what is now our Secondary Education center founded in 1990 with the entry into force of the LOGSE. Currently our center offers the teachings of CSE and Baccalaureate, as well as the Professional Training of "Electricity and Electronics", "Administration" and "Maritime Fishing Activities". With regard to this last title, it should be noted that it is one of the few centers that offers it in all of Spain.

2.1. Participants

In the 2021-2022 school year, 780 students are enrolled in our center who live with a faculty of 95 teachers. As we have mentioned before, this program is intended to help improve the digital competence of the components of the English department. Currently, the department is made up of 11 teachers aged between 35 and 45 years. Although, all of them have been using the digital book and various resources such as Google Classroom, Virtual Classroom, Idoceo, Kahoot, Liveworksheets, Quizzes, etc. for years most admit that their digital skills are quite limited and would like to improve. To find out where the teachers of the English department are in terms of digital skills, all of them submit to the digital teaching competence questionnaire, provided by the *Junta de Andalucía*. This questionnaire is carried out voluntarily and the participating teachers themselves are in charge of communicating their results to detect their needs and adjust this intervention program to their needs. The 11 participating teachers obtain similar results, according to the information provided to us, all of them are at an A2-B1 level according to the Digital Teaching Competence Reference Framework. Based on the results obtained, it is clear that the members of our department need a digital update. Thus, the creation of a project that helps our colleagues improve their digital skills and incorporate those digital tools that may be useful in their teaching work is vital.

Our project will be called "Digital Tools for English Language Teachers". This project is designed for English teachers at our center with the aim of creating a theoretical-practical proposal that adapts to the reality of our center. Our project is divided into different stages: analysis of the situation, preparation of the action plan, and implementation and evaluation of the process. In order to carry out this project and make it useful for our teachers, we have started from an analysis of its needs. As mentioned above, the first step has been to analyze the teaching digital competence of our classmates through the aforementioned questionnaire. The results of the test show a medium-low level of digital competence of our colleagues. The next step was to hold various meetings and interviews with the members of the department so that they could tell us about their shortcomings and those tools that they would like to know about. The third step was the development of the project according to the needs of our department

and presentation of the Training Plan to the management team. Being a completely voluntary training and to be carried out outside the working hours of our colleagues, it has not been necessary to include it in the Annual General Plan (PGA) of our center. Our project will be developed through the B-learning educational modality, alternating face-to-face evening workshops in our center and online activities. It should be noted that all the members of our department, except one due to schedule incompatibility since he is currently doing a master's degree, have joined our project. At all times we have tried to adapt to the needs and availability of each member of the department, even agreeing with them the number of weekly hours that were going to be dedicated to both face-to-face training and online activities and the content that we were going to work on.

2.2. Instruments

After a first contact meeting, it was agreed that the most appropriate thing would be to organize a weekly face-to-face session, at our work center, on Wednesday afternoons from 5 to 7 p.m., during the months of April, May and June. At first, it was planned that the project would be carried out at the beginning of the second term, but due to a sick leave of two of our colleagues, it was decided to postpone it until the end of April, coinciding with the return to class after the Easter holidays. The final timing was as summarized in the following table:

Table 1. Timing

Sessions	Date	Content
Session 1	20 th April	Tools for the virtualization of the English class
Session 2	27 th April	Oral comprehension tools
Session 3	4 th May	Oral production tools
Session 4	11 th May	Written comprehension tools
Session 5	18 th May	Written production tools
Session 6	25 th May	Miscellany
Session 7	8 th June	Evaluation tools

Source: Own elaboration

Let's go over now some of the principal instruments used in the program. The term Web 2.0 was first coined by DiNucci (1999) and later popularized by O'Reilly and Dougherty in 2004 during a conference discussing updating the existing web. It was noted that the Internet had become very popular and, in particular, that certain applications based on user interaction had grown exponentially. Web 2.0 essentially describes a second generation of Internet services, such as social networks, blogs, and wiki applications that emphasize online collaboration and sharing among their users.

It has been said that Web 2.0 goes beyond the limits of working on each user's local computer and enables collaboration on the world wide web. Websites have changed their design and promote interaction between users. In the past, the Internet offered the opportunity to create search and exchange activities. With the evolution of the Internet in the Web 2.0 environment, collaboration tools are offered that promote instant communication and interaction. An example of a Web 2.0 environment is social

networks, which are gaining more and more users by placing more emphasis on interaction than on content.

Some of the features that favor interaction are tagging, adding or editing links, searching for content on websites and, lastly, in some cases, the possibility for the user to intervene completely on a page, modifying its content, such as Wikipedia. The second-generation web architecture proposes to share digital production by groups - individuals.

With the evolution from Web 1.0 to Web 2.0, the tools available are innumerable and are constantly evolving as new applications are added every day. For this reason, only the main applications of Web 2.0 will be presented here:

- **Blogs:** Blogs are websites that are a form of expression for any Internet user who wants to present their thoughts online. The publications have the personal tone of the author and are arranged chronologically. The popularity of blogs is due to the fact that each user who visits them can post comments below the texts, thus offering positive or negative reviews, and the fact that creating a blog is free and extremely easy. Some tools for creating blogs are: Blogger, Tumblr, LiveJournal, Edublogs, Wordpress.

- **RSS:** The acronym RSS comes from the words Really Simple Syndication and describes a service that allows its users to keep up to date with news, events and events by sending the content of the posts of various websites that the user has selected at the time of publication. RSS has undergone significant development with the advancement of mobile devices (mobile phones and tablets) since the user can find out what interests him without needing a computer. Some additional RSS applications are: Feedburner, GoogleAlerts, FeedJournal.

- **Social Networks:** A social network can be considered to be any website that offers its visitors the possibility of creating profiles and interacting with other users through "social links" within an online community space. Social networks appeared hand in hand with Web 2.0. They can be classified into two main groups: vertical social networks, which include users with common interests and goals, and horizontal social networks, made up of members with different interests who are usually there simply to communicate, meet and interact. Some examples of social networks are Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and LinkedIn.

In addition to the categories mentioned above, there are other important categories of Web 2.0 tools such as: chat, concept maps, conferences, course development, file hosting, image processing, microblogging, personal file sharing, podcasts, games, presentations, contest development, recommendations, video tools, website creation and work organization.

Thanks to Web 2.0, teachers can address a new theory of learning and teaching that, unlike the classic platforms, is characterized by an excess of information and the freedom offered by the Internet. This type of technology aims to enhance creativity, information exchange and collaboration between users (Başal and Aytan, 2014). These three keywords really illustrate how the above concepts can be used in education. Web 2.0 tools can create a student-centered learning environment, as through them students have the ability to create their own knowledge and are not just passive recipients. They can also bring interactivity and dynamism to teaching and learning environments.

Additionally, Web 2.0 tools can improve classroom engagement by connecting students, teachers, and experts around the world. For example, with the help of Skype. Meet, Teams, etc., students can video conference in real time and collaborate despite geographical restrictions. Meanwhile, video sharing sites such as Vine and YouTube give them the opportunity to acquire information from professionals on various topics. They also give students the opportunity to produce their own creations and publish them on the web pages. Blogs offer the opportunity to encourage students to communicate

their thoughts and feelings and share their individual beliefs. This can improve learner autonomy (Başal and Aytan, 2014). Windeatt (1986) has analyzed the advantages of Web 2.0 tools and argues that computers can manage the demands of people, since they enhance inspiration, mainly in students who are not self-motivated, and can reduce the differences between the classroom and the outside world. In other words, Web 2.0 tools, if used properly, can positively affect the teaching and learning system.

However, there are some researchers who oppose the use of Web 2.0 in education, describing its tools as an "expensive luxury serving corporate interests" (Ellett et al., 1996). At the same time, since the inception of Web 2.0, serious concerns have been raised about the imminent exposure of students to dangerous websites that frequent Internet access can cause (Wartella & Jennings, 2000). Tardif (2002) underlines the fact that various educational activities, if supported by Web 2.0, with the same sequence and method, can be carried out more quickly and efficiently compared to traditional teaching.

However, previous research (Cuban, 2001) has argued that, although it is difficult to foresee the evolution of technology and teaching methods that will enter the school in the near future, a great effort must be made so that the tools of the Web 2.0 bring about fundamental changes in the educational process, since they are not a panacea. In addition, it has been found that a precise pedagogical design for new technologies in education has not yet been developed, as well as that there are deficiencies in teacher training (Pantano-Rokou, 2001). The research carried out by Fahandidis et al. (2004) concludes that most teachers, once the training is over, consider that their pedagogical training is not specialized in the use of technology. In conclusion, it is understood that the Web 2.0 is not enough for effective learning if there is not a complete curriculum, sufficient training, adapted educational materials and a well-structured social environment around it.

2.3. Data collection procedures

Due to the eminently practical nature of this project, directly related to the work of the members of our department, we have opted for the quintessential active methodology, known by its name in English "Learning by doing". During the workshops, the main functions of the different tools are briefly explained and then various activities are carried out to learn how they work by practicing. The second phase is carried out directly in the classroom, each teacher has to use the tools that they consider most used for their teaching practice and use them in class with their students. As we have specified previously, each week is dedicated to a different type of tools: virtualization of the class, oral comprehension, written comprehension, etc., so teachers have a week to work in their classrooms with the tools analyzed in each formative session.

Both the explanations given for the face-to-face sessions and the different tutorials for each tool used are recorded and uploaded to Google Classroom, the platform selected to share material, so that if you cannot attend a session or need extra support, teachers have it available. We must also point out that at any time teachers can consult their doubts through the department's WhatsApp group.

Once all the training sessions have finished, one last session is held, this time in the morning, since it is done once the classes and evaluation sessions of our center are finished. In this session, a sharing is done, the difficulties they have faced and the advantages and disadvantages that, according to them, the use of digital tools in the English classroom have been analyzed. This same session is also used to carry out the last phase of the project, the evaluation in which the teachers will fill out a satisfaction questionnaire.

2.4. Data analysis

As far as the analysis of the resources is concerned, the computers of our center have been used mainly, specifically we have held face-to-face sessions in the “*Aula Plumier*” of our center that has 25 computers, as well as the computers of the different classrooms where the members from the English department we teach on a regular basis. We must point out that during the blended learning period, in the 2020-21 academic year, the Ministry of Education equipped all classrooms with desktop computers, projectors and screens or digital whiteboards, microphones and cameras for synchronous classes.

Educational policies aimed at incorporating ICTs into schools in the Spanish context having a historical trajectory of more than a quarter of a century (Area, 2006). In a first stage in the eighties of the last century, these policies were promoted by the Spanish central government. The reference program of that time was called *Atenea*, later converted into PNTIC (National Program of Information and Communication Technologies). Subsequently, with the creation and consolidation of the governments of the Autonomous Communities and the transfer of powers in educational matters, regional policies and programs were drawn up, which were developed between the last decade of the 20th century and the first of the 21st century.

They were policies that followed European guidelines, because they were partly financed by the European Union, but although they coincided in many actions (providing computer rooms to schools, teacher training, production of digital educational materials, etc.), they were developed separately without an agreed plan or project for the entire Spanish territory.

However, during a brief period of three years (2009/12), we witnessed, in our country, an experience of coordinated national policy. Under the umbrella of what was called the “*School Program 2.0*”, similar goals, processes and budgets were shared in most of the autonomous communities of Spain. Policies were developed to bring a lot of technology into the classroom. These policies began to configure what became known as the “1 to 1 model”, that is, one computer per child (OECD, 2010). Initially, it was aimed at students in the 5th and 6th years of Primary Education. However, significant budget cuts in education to reduce the public deficit put an end to the *Escuela 2.0* Program in 2012.

Without a doubt, the role of the teacher in the introduction and use of technology in teaching is quite significant. One of the basic requirements is that teachers ensure that students make careful use of social networks and the Internet during the educational process, to avoid any inappropriate use. In addition, in the context of the student community, the teacher must create policies for the use of social networks and determine the consequences that result if they do not adapt to these policies. Consequently, teachers should introduce students to the world of social networks by suggesting that they use them sparingly and not indulge in unnecessary and prolonged use. In addition, before its use, objectives must be set for the realization of educational activities, so that the means can only be used for the indicated purposes. Therefore, the conditions of use of social networks and the privacy policy must be carefully studied by each teacher and student before using them.

The new technological era requires educators to be motivated to use technology during the language learning and teaching process. Teachers must have experience in the use of computers and must also know how to introduce digital tools in teaching (Li & Ni, 2011). Zhao, Tan, and Mishra (2001) point out that educational technology has long emphasized helping educators, not students. In fact, they claim that teachers are taught that technology is a tool to help them teach, which is more focused on conveying and communicating messages through presentation software rather than enabling students to acquire knowledge. According to Atkins and Vasu (2000), the general attitudes or concerns of teachers towards this subject greatly influence the use of computers in the classroom.

Furthermore, Redmond, Albion, and Maroulis (2005) report that teachers' personal backgrounds, such as personal confidence, interest in using ICT, and a desire to try something different, are vital factors that can promote the integration of ICTs in the classroom. Researchers from different parts of

the world believe that the use of ICT tools for educational purposes depends on the attitude of teachers towards technology (Albirini, 2004; Hamidi et al., 2014; Teo, 2008). Consistent with this statement, Summers (2010) believes that teachers' attitudes, skills, and work habits can have a major influence on their approval, implementation style, and effect of using computers for teaching.

As Zanguyi (2011) points out, the attitude of teachers towards the use of educational technologies in the teaching process is mostly positive. Similarly, Dogruer, Eyyam and Menevis (2010) found in their study that teachers think that the use of educational technology has a positive impact on their teaching experience. More importantly, Sharpe (2014) and Tsitouridou and Vryzas (2014) state that educators see technology adoption as a significant approach to improving education. However, Gillespie and Barr (2012) state that there are also teachers who only trust traditional teaching methods and are negative about the use of technology in education. Last but not least, these types of educators consider that the commitment to computer-based language learning is meaningless and they think that computers will not facilitate their work or reduce their workload (Burston, 2019).

Although there have been many studies examining teachers' attitudes toward technology (Bancheri, 2006; Love, 2005; McFarlane, Hoffman, & Green, 2017), research on student attitudes has been quite scarce (Aydin, 2011; Conole, 2008). As Blake (2018, p. 49) states, "since we use technology for language learning, we must also focus on how students use it and their attitudes towards technology based on their previous experience". According to Jaber (2007), the use of computers and the Internet in the classroom allows students to collaborate, use critical thinking and work together to find solutions to the problems they face. In addition, students are able to collect information for themselves, make decisions and be more independent (Lam & Lawrence, 2012).

There are many studies that mention how technology increases students' motivation to learn (Johns and Torrez, 2001). In general, students enjoy using the computer and therefore their motivation increases. In particular, the presence of information technology changes the way of teaching school subjects. In general, students are quite positive about the use of digital tools in the classroom and perhaps this is due to their familiarity with technology. In a study carried out by Ayres in 2002, it was found that students consider that computers cannot replace the traditional class, but they can complete it effectively. Technology can help them practice their grammar, writing, listening, and vocabulary skills through the use of exercises and homework found online. Finally, there are also some students who are not at all in favor of technology in education and, in this case, Jones (2011) suggests that teachers should offer students an alternative or some incentive to encourage them to use the tools. digital in the classroom.

3. Results

Before starting with the description of the sessions, it is essential to highlight three crucial aspects regarding the selection of tools:

- Only free tools have been selected and available to any user of both Android and IOS.
- All tools are easy to use.
- Those that can be easily integrated into the daily life of the members of the department and that serve as a complement and not to replace the digital book have been selected.
- This work is not intended to be a list of tools without further ado, but rather those that, in our opinion and according to the needs of the members of the department, may be most useful to them.

Session 1: Virtualization of the English class

This first session addresses the virtualization of the English class. We all have in mind the situation experienced by teachers worldwide when face-to-face classes were canceled due to the COVID-19 pandemic in the spring of 2020. Overnight, millions of teachers and professors had to figure out how to continue with their teaching work online. That was a turning point, when all teachers, with more or less digital competence, had to make a great effort to continue training the students and words hitherto unknown by many such as meet, videoconference, classroom, virtual environments, etc., became our day to day. Since then, aware of the fragility of face-to-face education, the interest in the use of digital tools in teaching has grown exponentially. So, in our first appointment we are going to address the different tools to virtualize a class.

For all this, it will begin with a review of the main virtual platforms used for the organization of classes both in the e-learning and b-learning systems. At this time, we must point out that only the platforms authorized by the Ministry of Education of the Region of Murcia will be analyzed, since private information about our students is shared in all of them. Currently, most centers in our autonomous community work with Virtual Classroom, Google Classroom and Teams, however some teachers use others such as Edmodo on a private level. Next, we will analyze in detail the utilities and the operation of each one of them.

The first platform that we find is Virtual Classroom, a tool provided by the Ministry of Education of the Region of Murcia and based on Moodle. Virtual Classroom allows you to upload and share all kinds of content with the students enrolled in each class, from videos, audios, glossaries, notes, tasks, questionnaires, etc. It has the particularity that students do not need to register since they access with their official *murciaeduca* email. The teacher only has to create the group and add the students from the Plumier XXI platform, the official platform where grades are recorded as well as each student, faults, coexistence and their educational needs. All the material added by the teacher becomes part of a repository that is stored indefinitely and can be reused in different courses or academic years. This platform is designed to share resources and activities with students but does not have any add-on for videoconferences.

In a very similar way to the Virtual Classroom platform, the Google Classroom educational web service allows you to create groups of students to share all kinds of material with them and communicate with students and families. It is a very simple and intuitive platform that students also access with their *murciaeduca* email, and the teacher can invite them through an email, a link or an access code. In Google Classroom, both teachers and students have a bulletin board to communicate with each other and a class work area where teachers can create topics, upload material, homework, quizzes, reuse material from other courses, etc. Students have access to the google calendar, to Drive, where all the materials uploaded by the teacher are stored and to all the G-Suite plugins such as Google Docs, Spreadsheets, Presentations and the Meet video conferencing tool that is integrated within Google Classroom.

Finally, TEAMS is perhaps the least used platform in the Region. It is a tool belonging to Microsoft but unlike Google Classroom, Teams does not focus on the creation of virtual classes but rather a communication platform that combines chat and video calls with which you can also exchange material with students, set homework, etc. Once the main characteristics of the three platforms have been analyzed, we call on the teachers to opt for one and use it the following week to share material and assign tasks to their students.

Session 2: Tools for oral comprehension (Listening)

The second session begins with a brief sharing of how each teacher has been working with the platform they chose during the first training session. On this second day we are going to delve into different digital tools that can be of great help to us to work on the oral comprehension of our students. For many of them, understanding oral texts is the most difficult of the four skills they must master. Unlike written

comprehension, oral comprehension occurs in real time and the speed at which information is received makes the task enormously difficult. In addition, students have to deal with a series of unknown accents, background noise interference and the pressure of having to respond to their interlocutor immediately, their own nervousness, etc. To all these factors we must also add the fact that unlike written comprehension, which can be checked over and over again, oral texts disappear once they are broadcast and students cannot listen to them again to reinforce their understanding.

Traditionally, the teacher tries to improve the comprehension of oral texts in the classroom through audio files and activities adapted to the level of the students. However, this is an area of language learning where digital technology and mobile devices can have a significant impact. Currently, there are a large number of websites and applications available for students to develop their listening skills independently, tools that can be used by teachers to create learning materials for their students.

The first tool that we are going to analyze is EDPUZZLE, it is a valuable tool that turns any video into an interactive class. It allows you to use videos from YouTube, Khan Academy, National Geographic, TED Talk, and Vimeo among others. Edpuzzle allows you to cut the video, insert an audio or insert questions along the video. Due to its great versatility, since it is the teacher himself who adapts it to his needs, Edpuzzle can be used both for class activities and to evaluate our students. It is important to note that the teacher can use it both with videos offered by the textbook and with any video that the teacher wants to include in a given lesson.

The second tool is very popular among students and teachers. This is LYRICSTRAINING, which combines listening to songs with learning a language. We must remember that the use of songs in the English class is an extended practice that is resorted to on a regular basis since it constitutes a tremendously motivating activity for students. Students can choose songs in various languages, watch the video of the song and try to reconstruct the lyrics. It is also possible to choose the level of difficulty, selecting if you want to reconstruct all the lyrics of the said song or just some words. The application introduces the different activities with the mechanics of the game. As students listen to the song, the music stops at the end of each line and they have a time limit to fill in the missing words. If they don't complete the line, they have to start over from the beginning of the song. The use of songs in this type of text reconstruction activity helps students to listen to them several times without getting bored. The app works in the web browser, but there is also a free app for both Android and iOS. Students and teachers can register on the website and the app will keep track of student scores. As a teacher, you can also add videos and lyrics of songs that you want to use with your students and thus add them to the LyricsTraining collection.

The third resource that we can use to improve our students' oral skills is TEACHVID, an application that combines listening with watching videos. This tool uses YouTube videos and builds a series of activities around them, ranging from text reconstruction, translation, multiple choice, jumbled sentences, among others. One of the main advantages is that students can choose the type of exercise they want. Another positive aspect that can be very useful for English teachers is that by registering they can create their own activities, share them with their students by creating "classrooms" and track their results.

Session 3: Tools for oral production (Speaking)

We inaugurate the month of May with our third training session, whereby the focus of our attention is on the tools to improve the oral skills of our students. Traditionally, the oral production of our students has perhaps been the skill that has been worked on the least in the English classroom, which has resulted in forming students with great grammatical training but with serious difficulties when speaking in English. Several factors have contributed to this situation: the high number of students per class that makes it very difficult to plan activities to practice "speaking", the reluctance of some teachers to use

English as the vehicular language in the class or the fact that in Spain there is a great culture of film dubbing that makes films that are a very valuable resource for practicing oral skills not be seen in the original version. Fortunately, this situation has been changing over the last few years and a determining factor has been the use of the internet and digital tools. Currently any student has access to innumerable resources that they can use on their way to mastering the English language. Among the wide variety of resources, we will highlight the following.

GOOGLE DOCS and its “voice typing” tool is a simple but tremendously effective resource that transcribes from voice to text in several languages with the push of a button. Once the English language is selected, our students can practice the pronunciation of different words, checking if the program is capable of “understanding” the student's pronunciation and correctly transcribing what they are dictating at any time.

In the same way that Google Docs has a dictation tool, Word has the “Read aloud” tool in which you can select the language, the type of voice and the reading speed, which can be useful to the student to hear the pronunciation of any word or text. This reading aloud can not only be done with word documents, but there are innumerable applications and devices that give us this option, such as the “read screen or document” function in the accessibility settings of both Android and iOS.

The next resource that we are going to analyze is called YOUENGLISH, which uses YouTube as a compilation of pronunciation examples. You simply type a word and it automatically detects YouTube videos in which the pronunciation of the said word appears. YouEnglish offers the possibility to choose between American, British and Australian videos, you can advance the video and go directly to the section where the word you are looking for is pronounced and even slow it down to hear it better.

For students with a more advanced level of English and with knowledge of phonetics, the PHOTRANSEEDIT website offers the phonetic transcription of any word or phrase. We must point out that it offers both the standardized British pronunciation known as Received Pronunciation or RP as well as the North American General American or GA and also the possibility of customizing the phonetic symbols by adapting them to the different phonetic transcription systems. In a very similar way, PHONETIZER, in addition to offering phonetic transcription, reads any text aloud with both a British accent and an American accent.

Another very interesting website is CLARISKETCH, with which students can take a photo, draw on it and record an audio describing the said photo or drawing. It is an interesting and funny way to make descriptions of photographs and send them to the teacher. It also offers the ability to share the descriptions on your website. It is completely free and has applications for iOS and Android.

FLIPGRID is a platform to encourage conversations between students. In a very similar way to Google Classroom, groups or classes are formed to which a discussion topic is sent in video format and they have to participate in the conversation by sending videos with their answers. It allows you to share the conversations through email, Google Classroom, Teams or through QR codes. It has a very attractive interface that can be customized for each group. It also has a repository of conversation topics.

The last tool in this section is LISTENWISE, a website that offers thousands of recordings of stories on a wide variety of topics that last between 3 and 6 minutes. The audio of these stories is accompanied by the transcript and interactive activities that can be adapted to the level of each student.

SYNTH is a tool that serves as an interesting way to make podcasts more interactive and engaging for students. You can record your podcast, a message, a question, or an audio file for your students to listen to and have them record a response or add to your message. It's a great way to gather knowledge together or create a dialogue with students while developing their listening skills.

Session 4: Tools for written comprehension (Reading)

Written comprehension is a skill that refers to a person's ability to read, understand, interpret and decode language and written texts. Exceptional reading ability can be very beneficial in assimilating and responding to written communications such as emails, messages, letters, and other written messages. Using written comprehension in the workplace can also be important in ensuring effective written communication, which can lead to fewer miscommunications or misunderstanding of expectations.

Reading comprehension can also encompass several key aspects that work together to build general literacy skills, including comprehension or the ability to understand what you read, fluency, vocabulary, and strategies that help readers interpret and find meaning of the texts.

In this fourth joint session we are going to study various digital tools to improve our students' written comprehension. Before starting studying the tools selected for today's session, we make a brief sharing to find out how the implementation worked in the last session. All the teachers of the department confirm that until now they are very satisfied with the different activities that they carry out in class and that the students are very motivated and expectant with the use of these digital resources that for all of them are totally new.

The first tool we are going to work with is called READLANG. It is a tremendously useful Google extension to help read texts. Once installed, you can read a text from your library, from a website or directly upload a text. Once uploaded, clicking on any word translates it directly on the line in which that term is found. All the selected words become part of a word list and cards or "flashcards" are automatically created for the student to practice. This tool can even be used with the readings that appear in textbooks, since most publishers offer the texts in word format or if they do not have it, the teacher can scan it with Google Lens and send the text to their students and either read it at home or in class. With this tool, the teacher can attend to the diversity of the students since each student can search for and store the words they need. It is very easy to use and although it does not have an application for smartphones, it can be used without any problem on any mobile.

LINGRO is intended for reading web pages. It does not require registering or downloading anything, you simply have to paste the web address and start reading. Every time we find an unknown word, we click on it and a pop-up window will appear next to it to the word with the definition or translation in the desired language. Like Readlang, the words are automatically saved in a word list with which you can also make flashcards.

Another tool that we can include in our classes and that can be of great help to our students is the REWORDIFY extension that converts any text into a much simpler version, which can help our students to be encouraged to read any type of text. This resource does not require signing up or registering on any site, the text or the URL is copied and automatically converted into a text with a simpler language.

If our objective is to work with authentic materials, we can use NEWS IN LEVELS, a web page that collects thousands of current journalistic articles classified in levels. It has the peculiarity that it also has the recording of each text to be able to listen to it.

We close this fourth session with SCRIBBLE, a Google extension that allows us to underline or highlight words, add notes, translate, read aloud any text on any web page. You only need to install the extension and when you enable it, it will appear at the bottom on the screen a toolbar with all these functions. In addition to all this, all the annotations, underlined words, etc. are saved in a personalized library that can be revisited by the student whenever necessary.

Session 5: Tools for written production (Writing)

This fifth session is dedicated to the last of the skills in which the teaching-learning process of the foreign language is traditionally divided, written production. With the arrival of mobile phones, written language has gained great importance since in most of the social networks used today, text is an essential component and the vast majority of written production is created with mobile devices. Thus, it seems natural that we look for digital tools that help us both in the production of these texts and in their correction. It is important to point out that many of these tools do not exist in the analog world, so it is essential that teachers help our students to get the most out of these tools and resources. Another significant change that digital text production has introduced is the ability to produce text collaboratively, both asynchronously and synchronously. In this section we are going to analyze a series of resources that will help you develop the digital writing skills of our students.

The first resource that is analyzed in this session is called INKLEWRITER, an application to create an interactive narrative that offers the reader the possibility to choose between several options. To start writing, you just have to click on the “Start writing” button, add a title and the first paragraph, and then it asks you for different options that the reader chooses. The application tracks the different options and continues your story.

In much the same way, the PLOT GENERATOR helps students create their own story. In the application a series of fields appear to be completed: title of the story, name of the protagonist, name of the secondary character, physical and psychological characteristics, place where the events take place, etc. and with all the information the application builds a narrative.

If instead of writing a narrative, the student has to write a newspaper article, FREENEWS PAPER GENERATOR can be of great help. It is a very easy-to-use web page in which you include the name of the newspaper, the article, your name, a photograph and the article and it automatically transforms it into a downloadable pdf document with the appearance of a classic newspaper.

We close the session with the web MYSTORYBOOK to create interactive stories. It is a web page in which we can create a book with the number of pages that we want, whose appearance we can modify on the models that the web provides us: backgrounds, landscapes, objects, photos, draw on them. And of course, texts can be added to which you can change the color, font etc. It is a free website that requires registration to be able to save all our creations and access them from the library where they are saved. This resource, a priori, has a somewhat childish aspect, but thanks to the great variety of modifications that it allows, it can be adapted to students of any age.

We cannot close this section of our program without mentioning the native tools that any word processing program provides us with when preparing any written production, such as spell checkers, word counters, format editors, integrated dictionary, etc. In addition, some of them, such as Google Docs, allow collaborative work, which facilitates the writing of texts among several students in a simple and intuitive way.

With today's class, we close the review of digital tools to work on the four traditional skills of the English class. Teachers are very satisfied and willing to incorporate many of these resources into their daily teaching work.

Session 6: Miscellaneous

We are in the final stretch of our program. This sixth session is dedicated to the study of several tools that are not directly related to the usual skills in which the teaching of English as a foreign language is divided. As usual, we begin the session with a discussion analyzing the positive and negative aspects of the tools that have been worked with the previous week. Once we have listened to the different experiences of our colleagues, we proceed to the analysis of the tools.

There are numerous websites and applications that are of great help to our students when it comes to understanding English grammar and syntax. The first tool that we are going to analyze is called TUBEQUIZARD. This tool uses authentic videos extracted from YouTube from movies, series, documentaries, interviews, etc., what will make something as dry as learning grammar be approached in a more attractive way. The website offers a large number of videos classified by level of difficulty (from A2 to C2), accent (American, British or Australian English), type of activity (vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, etc.) and video category (educational, society, news etc.). Each video has several exercises for students to complete while watching the video.

CLOSE TEST CREATOR is a website that allows us to create a fill-in-the-blank exercise from any text we want, being able to choose which grammatical category we want to practice: verbs, auxiliaries, prepositions, connectors, etc.

To facilitate the acquisition of vocabulary in a more attractive way for students we can make students, instead of copying tedious vocabulary lists in their notebook, make their own study cards with QUIZLET application with which they create their cards. They can add the definition of each word, the translation, photos from the same application or your own and then practice with various interactive games offered by the application. Another way to facilitate the acquisition of vocabulary is to use word clouds with applications such as MENTIMETER, WORD CLOUDS or WORDART that go one step further and organize the word cloud so that it forms drawings that will attract the attention of our students.

As for the collaborative tools and information exchange among the great variety that there are, we are going to highlight two for their ease of use: PADLET and MURAL. Both show an interactive mural in which students can add notes, texts, photos, drawings, audios or videos. They are two very interesting tools that can help us motivate students to do projects in a collaborative way that is much more attractive than traditional group work done on paper or with PowerPoint presentations.

If our objective is merely to share documents, photos, videos, audios, etc. with our students or for them to exchange material, we can use cloud storage systems such as Google Drive or Dropbox, which are perhaps the most used in our region.

Google Drive is a cloud storage system that has integrated applications for collaborative use: Google Docs, Google Presentations and Spreadsheets. The particularity is given that by an agreement between Google and the Ministry of Education of the Region of Murcia all users of the Region of Murcia, both students and teachers, with their “*murciaeduca*” user have unlimited storage capacity in Drive. It has an application for mobile phones and tablets. Similarly, Dropbox is another cloud storage system that allows us to store and exchange documents, although unlike Drive it does not allow online editing of documents. This limitation, together with the storage capacity mentioned above, means that the vast majority of teachers in the Region of Murcia use Google Drive to the detriment of other similar systems.

The sixth session ends with a demonstration of the QR CODE GENERATOR web, whose function is to create QR codes to project them in class and that students can scan to immediately access any resource that the teacher wants to share with his class. It is free and does not require registration and it can be downloaded as high-resolution PNG or a vector graphic.

Session 7: Tools for assessment and co-assessment

With this session we put an end to our training meetings in the evening hours. This last day, coinciding with the end of the course and the evaluation sessions, has been devoted precisely to evaluation. There are numerous applications and web pages intended for the evaluation of our students, but we are going to focus on those that are most common and easier to use. On the one hand, we are going to describe

some questionnaire-type tools, which serve both to practice any grammatical point or vocabulary with our students and to evaluate them, and on the other, those that we use as evaluation instruments.

Among the former, KAHOOT stands out, very popular with students and teachers. This website has a repository of questionnaires available to teachers. The vast majority are multiple-choice questions that students have to answer using their mobile phones. This web page adds a playful component to the questionnaires including music and a podium with the 3 winning students. Kahoot allows you to send quizzes as homework to students through Google Classroom or Edmodo, among others. Kahoot records the responses of each student and can be used as an evaluation tool.

In a very similar way, QUIZZIZ also provides multiple-choice quizzes, which can be sent as homework and also produces a report with the results of the students. It is basically an online-based quiz which operates like a gameshow. On the students' part, it makes learning more fun with game-based interactions in which they have to show their ability to work through a quiz using their own devices.

The third tool, very similar to Kahoot and Quizziz, is SOCRATIVE, with a somewhat less attractive interface but equally useful when evaluating students. Questionnaires can be assigned as homework and it allows monitoring the results in real time that can also be exported as a spreadsheet to analyze the results of each student. It is a digital tool built both for teachers and students which make learning interactions go online with certain ease. From a multiple-choice quiz to a question-and-answer pool, it provides teachers with instant feedback.

The last quiz-type tool we're going to cover is LIVEWORKSHEETS. It is a collaborative web page where we can find thousands of interactive and self-correcting worksheets made by teachers from all over the world. This website is not as attractive to students as the previous ones, since it lacks the playful component of the others, but it is a very valuable tool that allows students to be evaluated and encourage their autonomy, since they can practice on their own and see where they have made their mistakes. hits and misses.

We close the session with the analysis of two instruments for the elaboration of rubrics. In the English class they are usually used mainly to correct essays, oral exams, presentations, etc. The first is CORUBRICS, a Google extension that makes it easy to create rubrics from a spreadsheet. This sheet, associated with a Google form, allows us to evaluate our students in the most objective way possible and later analyze the results in the same spreadsheet. QUICK RUBRIC has the same function, only with a more attractive and intuitive interface.

4. Discussion

This didactic proposal arises from the socio-educational need to carry out innovative methodologies for the integration of new technologies in the classroom in the autonomous community of Murcia, through the subject of English as a foreign language. After analyzing the statements provided by the theoretical framework and the results obtained after the implementation of the program, we can conclude that the incorporation of technology and its tools in the teaching of English as a foreign language seems to have a positive effect both for students as well as teachers, so its introduction into the daily teaching practice of English teachers is necessary.

Among the benefits that we have observed after the use of the different tools analyzed during the training sessions, we could highlight the increase in motivation and commitment of the students, which has translated into an improvement in performance in general and in their behavior in particular. The students have been more attentive and expectant before the novelties that the members of the department have been introducing in their classes. The tools that have been best received are those in which the students had a more direct participation through their mobile devices and at the same time provided greater autonomy. We must point out that the reception has been very positive regardless of the age of the students in general.

Overall, English teachers in public secondary schools in the Region of Murcia have a positive attitude towards the implementation of technology and its tools in the classroom. We have to remember that our subject has always been a pioneer in the use of technology, from the use of boomboxes for listening comprehension activities in the early years, to later CD and DVD players, the incorporation of interactive digital books, language laboratories, etc.

The teachers participating in this program differ in age, teaching experience and digital training, but all of them are open to innovative ideas, which explains their favorable attitude towards this intervention program. From the reflections that have been sent to us, it appears that the teachers adopt an optimistic position regarding the integration of technology in secondary schools.

5. Conclusions

During the implementation of the didactic proposal, we have also encountered a number of limitations. The lack of time of the teachers participating in the project has meant that not all the tools discussed have been put into practice.

Common technical problems in the center have been encountered such as the failure of the Wi-Fi network at some particular time, the poor quality of some projectors and the broken speakers in one of the classrooms. The digital gap of our students also affected our study since we were teaching to fairly large groups, especially in 1st and 2nd of CSE, whereby some of them do not have their own mobile phone to be able to use it in class in some activities that require it.

We are aware that the Ministry of Education of the Region of Murcia has made a great effort to provide numerous devices to secondary schools, especially since the outbreak of the pandemic caused by COVID 19 a couple of years ago. However, there is still a large way to go to replace all the damaged devices or those that have become obsolete and specially to put an end to the digital gap suffered by some of our students since those belonging to the most disadvantaged classes do not have access to any digital media.

The advancement of technology and Web 2.0 tools has had different effects on almost all disciplines in the 21st century, and education is no exception. What this study has highlighted is that educators are now being encouraged to include digital media tools in teaching and learning tasks, especially in the context of English language learning. As far as the teachers participating in this project are concerned, they have seen first-hand the advantages of integrating digital tools in the English teaching-learning process.

An interesting proposal would be to extend this approach to the rest of the departments and hold workshops at the center the next school year. A possible future line of research could arise from this, which could be a case study that includes observation in the classroom and evaluation of the materials used. This would provide a richer view of the actual learning experience of students in the educational context of our center and help to gain a better understanding of how technology and its tools help students learn. In addition, a longitudinal study could be carried out on the implementation of technology in educational centers in the Region of Murcia, in order to improve the understanding of the attitudes of students and teachers towards the use of technology and discover its effect in student learning over a longer period of time.

Taking into account the above, it is important that teachers create a digitization program that favors integration action plans, including obtaining options (Gilakjani, Leong & Hairul, 2013). In addition, the technology plan must meticulously follow the objectives of the curriculum. Teachers need to be aware of which pedagogical method would be the most efficient when implementing digital tools in the classroom (Gilakjani, Leong, & Hairul, 2013).

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